

**Master Thesis:
fMRI Sonification
&
Brain Activity Prediction**

Imanol Gómez Rubio
Supervisor - Rafael Ramírez
Music Technology Group
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

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Abstract

The study of human brain functions has dramatically increased greatly due to the advent of functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging (fMRI), arguably the best technique for observing human brain activity that is currently available. However, fMRI techniques produce extremely high dimensional, sparse and noisy data which is difficult to visualize, monitor and analyze.

In this document, I propose a sonification approach for exploratory fMRI data analysis. The goal of this tool is to allow the auditory identification of cognitive states produced by different stimuli. The system consists of a feature selection component and a sonification engine. We will explore different feature selection methods and sonification strategies.

Moreover, I present a computational model which predicts the fMRI neural activation in humans produced by rhythm/no-rhythm auditory stimuli. The model was trained with acoustic features extracted from the auditory signals and the associated observed fMRI images. The obtained model is able to predict fMRI activation with high accuracy. This work represents a natural progression from building catalogues of patterns of fMRI activity associated with particular auditory stimuli to constructing computational models which predict the fMRI activity for auditory stimuli for which fMRI data are not available yet.

“The brain is a world consisting of a number of unexplored continents and great stretches of unknown territory” - Santiago Ramón y Cajal -

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Brain facts

A neuron is a basic cell capable of transmitting electric impulses. Once in a while one neuron, will spontaneously generate an electrical impulse or spike. As seen, one neuron by itself is hardly functional. It is the union of millions of neurons with billions of connections, that forms the complex human nervous system. The human brain is the center of the human nervous system. It integrates sensory information and regulates the body's actions and reactions. It is constantly monitoring and controlling all activities of the human body. From digestion, heartbeat, to more complex orders, such as the act of walking or swinging your arms. In fact, it is responsible of high cognitive states. The human brain is the seat of consciousness and reason. It's where the focus of learning, memory and emotion is.

But how is our mind built from such an enormous amount of neurons? How do our thoughts emerge from such a complex structure? 1.1

Despite all the advances, neuroscience is not yet able to answer these questions. Due to the enormous complexity of the brain, the development of suitable techniques constitutes an arduous task. The study of the brain can be approached from many levels of abstractions. Some researchers would devote their career to the study of single neuron's functioning. Others would study how a group of millions of neurons codify information, while others would solely focus on the study of mind and behaviour.

Fortunately, they have been able to find inspiration from other fields, like the stock market or computer circuits. Likewise, new mathematical tools have been developed

Figure 1.1: Abstraction of a brain network -

to analyse such complex systems, as well as the possibility to have new brain imaging techniques to extract non-invasively information from the brain.

Overall, the study of the brain will not only help, to understand human behaviour better, but also to discover ways to prevent many brain disorders, like schizophrenia or dementia.

1.2 Motivation and Goals

Many techniques have been developed to detect and measure neural activity in humans (e.g. EEG, fMRI, CAT) and various methods have been proposed for analysing the resulting data. In particular, **Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging (fMRI)** has been used extensively to test hypothesis regarding the **location of activation for different brain functions**. We will center the work on fMRI and its capacity to measure hemodynamic responses to changing stimulus or task conditions with a high spatial resolution over a time-scale of seconds.

The goal of **exploratory data analysis** is to render high dimensional data in

such a way that we can use our natural pattern recognition capabilities to search for regularities and structures. The common approaches have mainly focused on human visual capabilities. Many visualization techniques have been developed based on Self-Organizing Maps (Koh90), Multidimensional Scaling (RS00) and Projection Pursuit (FT74).

Motivated by the acknowledged human capacity to make accurate and rapid processing and discrimination of sounds, we will investigate the **auditory possibilities for exploring and analysing fMRI data**. Our first approach will propose a sonification tool to monitor and explore fMRI data. The goal is to allow the auditory identification of cognitive states produced by different stimuli. The detection of sequences of cognitive states can help in the diagnosis of difficulties in performing a complex task. We will implement a system consisting of: data analysis, feature selection, visualization and sonification. For the feature selection component we will study different feature selection methods, while for the sonification engine we will explore different strategies to map data into sound. We will apply the system to fMRI data produced by auditory stimuli consisting of rhythmic and non-rhythmic audio signals.

In comparison, while fMRI has been used extensively to test hypothesis regarding the location of activation for different brain functions, the problem of how human brain represents information and knowledge has been less explored. Research in human brain information representation has produced competing theories of how the human brain represents knowledge about different objects. Nonetheless, these theories are merely descriptive in that they make no attempt to predict the brain activation produced by the exposure to the stimulus in question.

Our second approach will present **computational models to predict fMRI neural activation** in humans produced by auditory stimuli. Various models will be trained with acoustic features extracted from rhythm/no-rhythm auditory stimuli and the associated observed fMRI images. Thus, the models will establish predictive relationship between the acoustic features extracted from the auditory stimuli and its associated neural activation. The ultimate model shown will be capable of predicting fMRI neural activity associated with the stimuli considered with accuracies far above those expected by chance.

1.3 Document structure

The material presented in this master thesis covers a number of aspects concerning techniques and applications of fMRI, Sonification, Machine Learning and Prediction Models. The document is organized in 6 chapters.

The first **Chapter (1)** contextualizes and explains the motivation and goals of the master thesis. The second **Chapter (2)** covers the theoretical background of the relations between brain and music (Section 2.1), general concepts of sonification (Section 2.2), functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging, (2.3), Machine Learning as an analysis tool 2.4 and dimensionality reduction, used to select the most relevant features (Section 2.5).

Chapter 3 reviews the state of the art relevant to the master thesis. That includes sonification as a data exploratory tool 3.1 and the analysis of fMRI data by machine learning methods (Section 3.2).

Chapter 4 explains the fMRI sonification approach. It presents the prototype implemented to that end, including the different voxel sonification techniques 4.4 and different feature selection methods 4.3 studied.

Chapter 5 is concerned with the brain activity prediction approach. It presents a computational model to predict neural activation in humans produced by auditory stimuli. There are three main sections: acoustic feature extraction (Section 5.1), model learning (Section 5.2) and model evaluation (Section 5.3).

The last **Chapter (6)** concludes both approaches summarizing them and proposes future work steps.

Chapter 2

Background

2.1 Music and the brain

All of us (without any neurological impairment) are born with the capacity to perceive music. The propensity to music is manifest and central in every culture and probably goes back to the very beginning of our species. While bird song has obvious adaptive uses, the origin of human music is not as easy to understand (Mur62).

At present, various adaptationist theories posit that the human capacity for music is a product of natural selection or even sexual selection, reflecting the survival value of musical behaviours in our species past (WB00). In contrast, Steven Pinker argues that music is a human invention and is biologically useless (Pin97).

However, it is known that our music capacities are obtained by different brain systems that have already developed for other purposes. This might go with the fact that there is **no single “music center”** in the human brain. Music takes many different forms, such as tones, timbre, pitch, intervals, melodic contours, harmony or rhythm. We integrate all of these and construct the music using many different parts of our brain. Overall, we can add the emotional reaction to music.

Unlike most other high-level functions of the human brain, only a minority of individuals become proficient performing musicians and through explicit practising. This extreme case of **skills acquisition**, is particularly interesting for the study of the brain plasticity (PZ03, PZ05).

The study of music perception and cognition is one of the oldest topics in experimental psychology. Yet, one of the first mentions of the subject was the publication by

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MacDonald Critchley and R.A. Henson's book *Music and the Brain* (CH77). But in the past decade there has been an increased interest on this topic, through functional neuroanatomy and using the latest neuroimaging technologies (LT09). Current trends are noted to be in the evolutionary origins of music (MH05) and the comparisons of music and speech (ZBP02).

2.2 Sonification

Sonification refers to the use of **non-speech audio** in order to **convey information** about data (Kra94). It is the scientific equivalent to visualization, but instead of converting data into illustrations according to uniform rules, it converts it into sound. Due to the characteristics of auditory perception, such as excellent temporal and pressure resolution, sonification provides an interesting alternative or complement to visualization techniques.

Sonification has been a well established technique in applications that require a constant awareness of some information (e.g. vital body functions during an operation). Success stories of sonification include the Geiger counter (GM28), auditory seismometers (Spe61) and medical auditory displays (ICV⁺06). More recent applications include information systems for impaired people (MBS11), human computer interfaces (FB04) and alternatives to visual displays (FS06).

By its nature, sonification is interdisciplinary, integrating concepts from human perception, acoustics, design, the arts, and engineering. Thus, development of effective auditory representations of data will require interdisciplinary collaborations of psychologists, computer scientists, engineers, physicists, composers, and musicians, along with the expertise of specialists in the application areas being addressed.

2.3 Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging

Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging (fMRI) is a brain imaging technique that allows the observation of brain activity in human subjects based on the increase in blood flow to the local vasculature that accompanies neural activity in the brain. The blood oxygen level is believed to be influenced by local neural activity, and thus this **blood oxygen level dependent (BOLD)** response is normally taken as an indicator

2.3 Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging

of neural activity. An fMRI scanner measures the value of the fMRI signal (BOLD response) at all the points in a **three dimensional image**.

An fMRI scanner produces time-series data that represents brain activity in a collection of 2D slices of the brain. The slices form a 3D image of the brain containing the order of 60000 voxels (volume elements), *i.e.* cubes of tissue about 2 millimeters on each side. Images are usually taken every 1-5 seconds. Despite the limitations in temporal resolution, fMRI is arguably the best technique for observing human brain activity that is currently available. While the **spatial resolution** of fMRI is dramatically better than what provided by earlier brain imaging methods, each voxel nevertheless contains on the order of hundreds of thousands of neurons. Figure 2.1 shows fMRI data collected while a person listened to auditory stimuli.

Figure 2.1: fMRI data collected while a person listened to auditory stimuli - The figure represents nine 2D slices from a 3D image of the brain. Every slice is 64x64 voxels and their intensities are represented with a "jet" colormap. This colormap begins with blue (lowest intensity) , and passes through cyan, yellow, orange, and red (highest intensity).

fMRI has been widely applied to the task of identifying the regions in the brain

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which are activated when a human performs a particular cognitive function. Most of the reported research summarizes average fMRI responses when a human is presented with a particular stimulus repeatedly. Regions in the brain activated by a particular task are identified by comparing fMRI activity during the period where the stimulus is presented with the activity detected under a control condition. The aim, therefore, is to deduce that stimulus that cause brain activity with a certain intensity and location.

2.4 Machine Learning

If a machine improves its behaviour with experience, we might say that it has learned. **Machine Learning (ML)** is a branch of Artificial Intelligence (AI) concerned with the design and development of algorithms that allows computers to improve its behaviour based on incoming data, or experience 2.2.

Figure 2.2: Machine Learning Abstraction -

A major focus of machine learning research is to **automatically learn** to recognize complex patterns and make intelligent decisions based on data. This can be used in many applications like medical diagnosis, search engines, games, robotics or data

analysis in general.

In fact, it provides useful tools, when dealing with large quantities of data. If the amount of data exceeds the amount that a human can process, we need to develop computer systems able to find the relationships inherent in the data, or even, be able to draw conclusions from the data. An autonomous system with these characteristics would gain an independence that will allow it to perform beyond simple mathematical calculations.

Machine Learning methods are commonly used for **classification** purposes when the variables to be predicted are discrete, or **regression analysis** if the variables are continuous. More concretely a classifier is a function that takes the values of various features (independent variables or predictors, in regression) in an example (the set of independent variable values) and predicts the class where example belongs to (the dependent variable).

The instances of a dataset used by machine learning algorithms are represented using the same set of features. If the instances are given with known labels (the corresponding correct outputs) then the learning is called supervised, in contrast to unsupervised learning, where instances are unlabeled.

Supervised learning consists, fundamentally, of two steps. The first step is the training phase, where the system looks for the most relevant features and creates a model capable of making decisions. The second step is adaptation, in which the system analyses the decisions taken, according to the model created and using known information. It, then, refines the model based on differences found in the evaluation. The output can be either a numeric value (as in regression problems) or a label that identifies a particular class (as a classifier). Well known supervised learning algorithms are Artificial Neuronal Networks (ANN), Support Vector Machines, k-Nearest Neighbor (K-NN), Mixture Models (MM), Naive-Bayes classifiers or decision trees. For our work we will focus on Support Vector Machines (Section2.4.1).

In contrast, **unsupervised learning** differs from supervised by the fact that there is not initial knowledge of the data. Typically, unsupervised learning algorithms, treat the input data as a set of random variables, and construct a density model for the data set. It can be used in conjunction with Bayesian inference to generate conditional probabilities for any variable. It is also useful for data compression since many of the

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compression algorithms rely on the probability distribution of the input set. It is also used to cluster groups of data similar to each other, depending on proximity criteria.

2.4.1 Support Vector Machines and Regression

The **Support Vector Machines** (SVM) are classifiers that belong to supervised learning methods. The original algorithm was invented in 1992 by Vladimir Vapnik and his team at AT & T Laboratories (BGV92, VGS96), and became famous quickly, giving a much higher performance than neural networks in recognizing handwriting.

It is based on the statistical learning theory, which contains polynomial classifiers, neural networks and radial basis functions. A Support Vector Machine **constructs a hyperplane in a high dimensional space** by the use of a **kernel function** that it is used to transform data from the input (independent) to the feature space. There are number of kernels that can be used in SVM models, including linear, polynomial, radial basis function (RBF) and sigmoid. The optimum separation will be the one that maximizes the distance between the two classes, and allows a correct classification. The algorithm is based on guaranteed risk bounds of statistical learning. Overall, by choosing a suitable kernel function the separation between the hyperplane and classes, known as margin, will increase, thus reducing the error of the classifier.

Support Vector Regression (SVR), proposed in 1996 by Vladimir Vapnik et.al (DBK⁺97), describes function estimation with support vector methods. The idea of SVR is based on the computation of a linear regression function in a high dimensional feature space where the input data are mapped via a nonlinear function. SVR is one of the most common application form of SVMs and it has been applied in various fields, *i.e.* time series and financial prediction, approximation of complex engineering analyses, convex quadratic programming or choices of loss functions.

2.5 Dimensionality Reduction

The dimension of the data is the number of variables that are measured on each observation. When dealing with high-dimensional datasets, it is often advantageous to **reduce the number of features** considered to focus on a subset of particular interest. Various techniques have been implemented to that purpose where they commonly transform the original feature space into a new, low-dimensional feature space. The goal

is to improve the performance of the predictions, provide faster and more cost-effective predictors, and give a better understanding of the underlying process that generated the data.

There are several generic methods for linear dimensionality reduction, like Principal Component Analysis (PCA) (Jol86) or Independent Component Analysis (Com94), as well as higher-order methods, like projection pursuit (FT74). However, it is not at all guaranteed to improve the classification results, partially because these techniques ignore class labels in their criteria. Supervised methods are then used, when selecting the most informative features. **Very common techniques in neuroimaging** for detecting brain areas which are relevant for particular cognitive tasks are the **student T-test** (Section 2.5.1) and **Analysis of variances** (ANOVA) (Section 2.5.2). In this work we apply these techniques in order to perform feature selection for sonification purposes.

2.5.1 T-test

A **T-test** is any test where the quantitative measured (derived from a set of samples) has a Student T distribution if the null hypothesis is true. It is applied when the population is normal but the sample size is too small for statistic purposes (quantitative measurement). It is often used to compare two small sets of quantitative data when samples are collected independently of one another.

The **t value** can be calculated as shown in equation 2.1

$$t = \frac{\bar{x} - \bar{y}}{\sqrt{\frac{Var(x)}{N_x} + \frac{Var(y)}{N_y}}} \quad (2.1)$$

where \bar{x}, \bar{y} , $Var(x), Var(y)$ and N_x, N_y are respectively the mean, variance and sample size of variables x, y .

The value is maximized for distributions whose expected values are as far as possible and also to the smallest variance possible. By the time we need to choose the best voxels, we will employ those with the highest T-value.

2.5.2 ANOVA

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) is a statistical test for heterogeneity of means by analysis of group variances. It is used to test hypotheses about differences between two

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or among more means. On the contrary, the T-test can only be used to test differences between two.

The method used in this master thesis is called the **one-way analysis of variance**, and the test statistic is the **F ratio**. In fact, T-tests are a special case of ANOVA. By analysing the means of two groups with ANOVA, the results are the same as in the equivalent T-test analysis. The name analysis of variance comes from the way the procedure uses variances to decide whether the means are different.

Chapter 3

State of The Art

3.1 Sonification for data exploration

With abundance of high-dimensional data, **auditory data exploration** has become an important tool to comprehend such data and to uncover its structures and patterns (HHR01, BK99). Thus, sonification has expanded beyond the classic process monitoring applications and **many researchers among different fields are currently researching in this area.**

Vogt et al. (VBHdC08) used sonification to understand lattice quantum chromodynamics (QCD) as a representation of a 4 dimensional space. Grond et al. (FG10) implemented a combined auditory and visual interface to help browsing ribonucleic acid (RNA) structures. Winters et al. (RMW11) simulated through sound the phase transition that occurred shortly after the Big Bang. Bearman (Bea11) used sound to represent uncertainty in future climate predictions. Finally, Alexander R. (AGS⁺11) was able reveal new insight into data parameters for differentiating solar wind types, by audifying and listening to 13 years of heliospheric measurements.

Sonification is particularly appropriate to improve the understanding of **biomedical data**, which is naturally multidimensional. More concretely, sonification of neuroimaging data has been widely used for the study of the brain. Most of these studies so far have focused on analysing the data obtained from **Electroencephalography (EEG)** measurements, but to the best of our knowledge, there has been **no similar research projects based on fMRI data** reported in the scientific literature.

One of the first attempts to auditory EEG exploration was reported in 1934 by

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E. Adrian and B. Matthews (AM34). For their research they measured the brain activity from a human subject by electrodes applied to the head, and the channels were viewed optically on bromide paper using the Matthews oscillograph, while being directly transduced into sound. They were able to show the synchronization between brain activity and external stimuli.

More recently, T. Hermann et al. in 2002 (HMB⁺02) presented different strategies of sonification for human EEG. Those were *spectral mapping*, by analysing the spectral properties of the signals; *Distance Matrix Sonification*, using the Euclidean distance among all signals; and *Differential Sonification*, where they compare the data from different conditions and different channels.

In (BH04) T. Hermann and G. Baier analysed the rhythmical structure of EEG using auditory exploration. They used a set of differential equations to process the data and extract the parameters to feed the Model-Based Sonification (HR99). In 2006 T. Hermann and G. Baier (HBSR06) used an articulatory speech model driven by variable features. Both personalized and generic features were used, such as transient activity, spatial distribution or correlation matrix features. T. Hermann and G. Baier also explored multi-channel sonification (BHS07). The system was intended to allow the listener to perceive spatial characteristics of the data in a multi-speaker environment. They explored the idea of *Event-Based Sonification* (EBS), where features are defined as events that trigger sound synthesis. In this case, local maxima was thought to be suitable both for real-time sonifications and meaningful to the clinician.

There have also been attempts to translate human EEG into music. D. Wu et al. worked to represent mental states by using music (WLY⁺10). The EEG features were extracted by wavelet analysis and they would control musical parameters such as pitch, tempo, rhythm, and tonality. To give more musically meaning, some rules were taken into account like harmony or structure. One of the main challenges of this work was to find the precise trade-off between directly sonification of the features and music composition.

Finally, **several tools** have been recently developed to explore data streams through sonification. This is the case of Sonifyer, a user's interface for listening to data, mainly based on audification and FM synthesis (DBF⁺08). Two other recent sonification tools are AeSon Toolkit, motivated by user-centred customisation of the aesthetic represen-

tation and scope of the data(BF09), and SUMO (GD08) for the sonification of chemical data.

3.2 fMRI and Machine Learning

fMRI has been widely applied to the task of identifying the regions in the brain which are activated when a human performs a particular cognitive function. Interpreting fMRI experiments requires analysis of complex, multivariate data, since it provides a time series of samples for each voxel in the scanned volume. A variety of methods are used to correlate these voxel time series with the task in order to produce maps of task-dependent activation (Figure 3.1). An analysis approach that has grown in popularity is the use of **machine learning algorithms** to train classifiers to decode stimuli, mental states, behaviours and other variables of interest.

Figure 3.1: fMRI time series slices - fMRI scanner images can be presented as collection of 2D matrices, where every position represents a time series.

Conventional statistical methods for fMRI, analyses each voxel' s time series independently (“univariate analysis”). An example is **General Linear Modelling** (NW72), where a model is set up (*i.e.* a general pattern which you expect to see in

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the data) and fitted into to the data. However, disparate regions of the brain do not operate in isolation and **multivariate analysis** is getting more popular. These methods process all the data together and therefore make more use of spatial relationships within the data than univariate analysis.

A brief overview of this method is as follows:

1. **fMRI experiment:** Designing a neuroimaging experiment and extracting the data (Section 2.3).
2. **Data preprocessing:** It can include registering the images, motion correction, and spatial and temporal smoothing to improve the signal to noise ratio (Section 4.2).
3. **Creating examples:** this step decides what to use as features, how to extract their values from data and what we would like to predict. In a usual setting the features could be voxels and the class could be the type of stimulus the subject was looking at when the voxel values were recorded. However, we are not limited to use voxels as features. We could use the average of several voxels in one ROI as a single feature or consider each voxel at each time point in a trial as a different feature.
4. **Feature selection:** the idea here is to reduce the number of features considered to focus on a subset of particular interest, given that there are generally many more features than examples (Section 2.5).
5. **Train the classifier:** The first step is to choose the proper classifier (*i.e.* Linear Regression, SVM, Artificial Neuronal Networks, ...) and then fit the classifier with a training set. Cross validation might be used to train the algorithm with as much data as possible, leading to a better estimation.
6. **Test the classifier.** This section is concerned with two major issues: determining how well a classifier performs (and whether it is better than random) and drawing conclusions from multiple classifiers trained and tested on the same data.

There are many general reviews on multivariate statistical analysis, machine learning and fMRI (Row06, PMB09), while other works have reviewed, more general aspects

of decoding mental states and pattern analysis (NPDH06, HR06, FSD06, MBK09). In contrast, some works have focus on more specific aspects, like ROI-based fMRI classification (EGK09).

Multivariate analysis have been performed on fMRI data using different types of stimuli. Most of the studies so far have focused on analyzing the data obtained from **visual stimuli** (HGF⁺01, KT05, MHN⁺04). Nevertheless, auditory data analysis with multivariate analysis has recently gained interest, as seen in the works done by Ramirez et al. (RP07) and by Grahn and Rowe (GR09).

In addition multivariate analysis have also been used for “**mind-reading**” techniques. In these kind of studies the classifier tries to predict what the subject is responding to by looking at the brain activity (HR05, TDH⁺06).

Moreover, **additional techniques** have also been developed for fMRI analysis, including including Granger causality (RFG05, GRKF03), Bayesian inference (FP07, WBB⁺04), multivariate spectral analysis (MLBvC01) and multivariate regressive models (HPF03).

Numerous **software** are also available for performing multivariate processing. Some can be found at pyMVPA (HHS⁺09) http://www.py_mvpa.org/, princeton-mvpa-toolbox <http://code.google.com/p/princeton-mvpa-toolbox/> and Opani’s mvpa <http://opani.com/neuro/mvpa/>.

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Chapter 4

fMRI Sonification

Figure 4.1: fMRI Sonification - Steps followed on the fMRI Sonification approach. First of all, the data is preprocessed to reduce noise and other unwanted features. Secondly, the most relevant features are extracted. Finally, the features are sonified, along with the visualization tools.

fMRI provides the user with information on the location of functional activations in the different regions of the brain. The resulting data is high dimensional, sparse and noisy and leads to a difficulty to monitorize it and detect structures or patterns. This fact has motivated the approach to improve the exploratory data analysis. The main goal is to use sound to render the original data in a suitably transformed way, so that we can invoke our natural pattern recognition capabilities in order to search for regularities and structures. Additionally, we have combined sonification with visualization providing better tools for exploring and inferring such data. Part of the work explained in this chapter has been published at the 17th International Conference on Auditory

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Display (**ICAD-2011**) (GR11) and it is attached on the Appendix 6.2.

Figure 4.1 shows the steps followed on this approach, which are explained in the next sections. Firstly, the data acquisition (Section 4.1), secondly the preprocessing (Section 4.2), then the feature selection step and finally, the voxel sonification (Section 4.4). To conclude, the results are shown in Section 4.5 and discussed in Section 4.6.

4.1 Experiments and Data

All the data used in this master thesis was created at the experiments done by Grahn and Rowe in 2009 (GR09). In their work they used **fMRI images** to study the perception of rhythm in musicians and non musicians.

In their experiments several subjects had their brain activity measured, while exposed to volume accented and duration accented **rhythmic stimuli**. The stimuli were between 14 and 18 s long. There were four rhythm types: volume beat, volume non-beat, duration beat and duration non-beat. Thus, the first rhythm type (Volume accented with Beat) consisted of 81 tones, in which every 4th tone was louder by 6.6 dB, in order to give rise to the perception of a regular beat (occurring 21 times per trial). For each trial, the tone length was chosen from a range of 180 to 228 ms (in 8 ms steps) so that a new beat would be induced in each trial, not simply carried over from a previous trial. Accordingly, the beat occurred at a rate of 720 to 912 ms. The second rhythm type (Volume accented with no beat) also had 81 tones. However, the tone volumes were not isochronous, so no regular beat could be fit to the rhythm.

The data acquisition was done using a 3T Siemens Tim Trio MRI scanner and produced over five hundred 3D brain images for each subject and test. Every volume was composed of around 140.000 voxels (Volumetric Picture Element), representing cubes of tissue of 3 millimetres on each side. Each image was taken every 2.19 seconds and divided into 36 slices, composed by a 64x64 matrix. All the data was finally turned into **NIfTI-1 Data Format** provided by Neuroimaging Informatics Technology Initiative.

4.2 Preprocessing

Every brain image obtained, contains thousands of voxels, but many of them do not make any contribution. In fact, most of them are located outside the head, and many others correspond to parts of the anatomy that do not belong to the brain, as might be the skull. Therefore, the *non-relevant* voxels were **filtered out** and not taken into further processing.

On the other hand, the subject's head could have moved, which brings changes in voxel intensities. This is one the major source of artefact in fMRI data. It is common, therefore, in fMRI data analysis to perform some correction to reduce this effect. SPM8 software (Wellcome Department of Imaging Neuroscience, London, UK) was used for the **motion correction** process. Images were automatically synchronised and interpolated in time to correct for acquisition time differences and realigned spatially with respect to the first image using trilinear interpolation.

Any reduction in the random noise in the image improves the ability of a statistical technique to detect real activations and reject false ones. **Spatially smoothing** each of the images improves the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). The smoothing was implemented as a convolution with a three-dimensional Gaussian kernel, applied uniformly over each entire volume. The Gaussian kernel followed the form 4.1, where s_x , s_y and s_z are the standard deviation of the gaussian in each direction.

$$f(x, y, z) = \exp\left\{-\left(\frac{x^2}{2s_x^2} + \frac{y^2}{2s_y^2} + \frac{z^2}{2s_z^2}\right)\right\} \quad (4.1)$$

Nevertheless, there is no straightforward answer to the question of which is the best smoothing width to use in the analysis of the data set. A gaussian kernel of size ϱ represents a compromise between improving the SNR and spatial resolution of the functional image.

As well as smoothing in the spatial domain, improvements in the signal-to-noise ratio can be made by smoothing in the temporal domain. The output signal can have a number of slow "scanner drifts," where the mean of the data drifts up or down gradually over the course of the session, which are too low to correspond to BOLD signals. It is also the case that the signal oscillates much faster than it should for BOLD signals, giving artificial high-frequency components. Therefore, for the **temporal smoothing**,

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we have applied a band pass filter to the signal to restrict it to a specific band of frequencies.

4.3 Feature Selection

Neuroimaging data usually has a lot of features and fewer examples. Hence, it is desirable to reduce the number of features using feature selection techniques. As the cognitive state identification task clearly involves a high dimensional training data, before any attempt to sonification it is necessary to apply feature selection methods. For our purpose the voxels (Volumetric Picture Element) will be the features to extract. We want to know how important are the voxels of a certain region according to the tasks.

The strategy used has been **voxel discriminability**. For each voxel and considered cognitive state, a **t-test** (Section 2.5.1) is performed comparing the fMRI activity of the voxel in examples belonging to the two stimuli of interest. In the case of more than two cognitive states, instead of the t-test, **ANOVA** (Section 2.5.2) is performed comparing the fMRI of the voxel in examples belonging to the different stimuli of interest. n voxels are then selected by choosing the ones with larger t-values or f-values.

The feature selection strategy is motivated by the fact that fMRI binary cognitive state identification problems naturally give rise to different types of data (similarly for non-binary identification problems). That is, data corresponding to the different labelled classes including the fixation condition. In this case, data corresponding to the different classes is composed of signal plus noise, while data corresponding to the fixation condition contains only noise. Thus, voxel discriminability is a natural feature selection method, *i.e.* how precisely the feature discriminates between two classes (t-test) or among different classes (ANOVA).

However, both techniques are dependent on the mean and variance of each variable. Furthermore, both approaches only evaluate each voxel separately. Thus, it might be interesting to explore other type of discrimination criteria, aside from the mentioned statistical moments, and multivariate analysis, which is processing all the voxels together. To that end, Machine Learning techniques result more than convenient. Specifically, we have used the **weights of Support Vector Machines** as a discrimination criterion.

Linear SVM assumes that the distribution of the different classes is such that they are linearly separable. This can be conveniently expressed by a hyperplane in the space X , where $x \in X$, *i.e.* we are looking for a function f of the form 4.2,

$$f(x) = (w^T x) + b \quad (4.2)$$

where w denotes the weight normal vector to the hyperplane. The squared weights provides a mechanism for ranking relative importance of each feature to the classification. The features with larger weights are deemed to be the most useful for discrimination. This technique is often used in SVM-Recursive Feature Elimination (GWBV02).

4.4 Voxel Sonification

The core of sonification are the processes and algorithms that define the mapping of data to sound for any particular application. The term mapping refers to mathematical transformations applied to real-time data received from controllers or sensors so that they may be used as effective control for sound synthesis parameters.

For our purpose, we have used **Parameter-Mapping Sonification**, in which data values are mapped to the various parameters of a sound. This approach is particularly suited for multivariate representation, as many data dimensions can be listened to at the same time. Nevertheless, connecting the parameters to components of a real-time sound engine is not trivial.

The sound waveform has various attributes (*i.e.* frequency, amplitude, phase, envelope, spectrum, shape, velocity, wavelength ...) that can be modified to generate audio. For instance, we could relate the waveforms amplitude to the magnitude of the seismic activity. Besides, we can explore mapping to sound synthesis parameters as well. For example, synthesis by amplitude modulation (AM) involving a carrier and a modulator, as well as frequency modulation (FM), additive synthesis, filters, effects, *etc.* Complementary to that, sound spatialization adds even more dimensionality and options for system designers. Finally, musical parameters, *i.e.* tempo, rhythm, time signature or tuning, could be useful to enhance structure patterns and provide more aesthetics to the sound.

To effectively perform a musically satisfying mapping, we must understand well the nature of the data sources and the nature of the sounds and music we want to produce.

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This poses significant problems in the case of biologically controlled sonification in that the goal is to have an unambiguous interpretation of the meaning of biological signals whether direct or derived. Moreover, we should ask ourselves, how should human brain activity sound? how consistent would a sonar interpretation be for various listeners?

As a first approach the sound synthesis technique has been based on **additive synthesis**, where the output sound is created by combining basic signal generators. The first sonification strategy proposes mapping features energy level to frequency components and using a large number of features, approximately 200. The idea is to create a sound texture, that would faithfully represent the data hidden patterns that would turn into periodic sounds. More concretely, the normalized energy from every feature was mapped to the frequency of a sine tone within the range of 50Hz-15.000Hz. A fragment of the sound spectrogram can be seen in Figure 4.2.

Figure 4.2: Sound spectrogram fragment of additive synthesis approach - Sound spectrogram fragment from the second sonification approach. The x and y axes represent time and frequency respectively, and the color represents the intensity of the frequency components. The horizontal lines show the partials mapped from the selected features and the vertical lines is the consequence of the abrupt transitions between time slots.

The next proposed strategy takes into account **harmonic constraints**, specifically from western music. In fact, the purpose is to recreate the inner structure of the selected features using “consonant” and “dissonant” intervals. It works on the assumption that

consonant intervals create a feeling of stability sounding pleasant or melodious, whereas dissonant intervals create a feeling of instability sounding harsh or unpleasant together.

As it is understood in common-practice, in tonal music the perfect fifth and the perfect octave are considered perfect consonances, while the major third and sixth, as well as the minor third and sixth, might be considered as imperfect consonances. In contrast, major and minor seconds, sevenths, and ninths are said to be dissonant. As well, the perfect fourth is considered dissonant in common practice music when not supported by a lower third or fifth.

This sonification approach works as follows. Every selected feature controls the level of a single note within a chosen tonality and within several octaves. Every feature is normalized by its energy activation range to avoid preferences on higher energetic features. The features are not selected to random notes, but rather are connected to more or less stable notes according to their deviation from their mean. That is, the stable features will be related to consonant intervals and the more unstable to dissonant intervals. The result shows a **17-voice continuous sound texture**, created at every instant with different pitch and loudness, representing the activation patterns of the selected features.

The third strategy follows the same rules explained on the harmonic strategy, but avoiding the sound to be continuous. At every instant of the experiment a **chunk of sounds** with linear decay is created. The idea is to keep sound events as short as possible in order to prevent interference with other sounds and to avoid sound masking. This concept exploits the capacity to distinguish discrete sounds and comparing them to previous ones.

In the last proposed strategy, we have explored the idea of using the data as a **brain computer interface**, that would control parameters used by musicians. In this case, every selected feature controls a different parameter. These are, the pitch of the synthesized sound, a low frequency oscillator (LFO) modulator of the sound, a band pass filter attached and a drum loop, triggered when reaching certain thresholds. It is meant to be a trial of a computer-music system that interacts directly with the user's brain.

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4.5 Results

As the result of the work explained in Chapter 4, a **prototype tool** (Figure 4.3) was implemented for visual and auditory fMRI exploration.

Figure 4.3: fMRI Data Interface. - The plots at the top and at the bottom left represent three different slices of a 3D image of the brain, according to the X,Y, Z axes. The fourth plot represents the energy of the voxel selected by the user, across time. The bottom panel is used as a video player and the left panel shows different information about the system and the selected voxel.

The graphical interface is based on video player softwares, but in this case, the user is able to watch and listen to the brain activity across time. At any moment the user can play or stop the video, as well as select any precise instant of reproduction or control the playback speed. The visual output corresponds to the 3D fMRI scanner image, divided in four plots: three slices representing the x, y and z planes of the selected voxel and a fourth plot for its energy level through time. The interaction in real-time with the data is one of the key points of the prototype. It lets the user interactively select any voxel of interest by clicking on the plot or to choose any form the list of selected features. Moreover, it permits to choose in real-time among different feature selection methods (Section 4.3) and different sonification techniques (Section 4.4) to

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4.6 Discussion

The implemented prototype has the objective to create a **tool for advanced analysis, visualization and sonification of fMRI**. To that end, the visualization tools have been based on professional neuroimaging software such as BrainVoyager QX <http://www.brainvoyager.com/> or FSL View <http://www.fmrib.ox.ac.uk/fsl/>. The feature selection methods chosen (Section 4.3) are state of the art techniques used for fMRI analysis with Machine Learning. Finally, the sonification techniques (Section 4.4) are meant to enhance the ability to explore and understand multivariate data. Nevertheless, to improve the quality of the system there is a necessity to have constant evaluation and collaboration with neuroscientist to solve any possible design issues.

About the **feature selection methods**, they seem to offer enough information suitable for sonification parameters or to train a classifier. Figure 4.5 depicts the activation level of a single voxel in time. The colors represent the different type of stimulus to which the subject was exposed. As seen in Figure 4.5, it is possible to graphically observe some patterns on the voxel's activity. For instance, we can notice that the dark blue lines tend to remain above the light blue lines, whereas the dark green lines tend to remain under the light green lines.

Figure 4.5: Voxel activity - The graphic represents a single voxel activity every brain volume measured. The y axis represents voxel activity and the x axis consecutive frames. The green lines represent time where the subject was attending to duration accented stimuli, while the blue lines represent the volume accented stimuli. The gray part represents the resting time between two different stimuli.

Referring to the different **sonification techniques** (Section 4.4), the additive synthesis approach resulted in a rather noisy sound, due to the lack of harmonic restrictions. However, it renders with sound a large amount of features at the same time. Furthermore, any hidden structure of the data might stand because of the human capacity to rapidly distinguish periodicities in the sound.

On the other hand, the harmonic strategy produced a complex polyphony made of individual parts, in a clearly discernible interval combination. From this cloudiness, it is possible to discern changes in the data. In contrast, to the additive synthesis approach the number of selected features must remain low. This limitation helps to keep the sense of harmony and not to overload the user with too many sound information. When creating chunks of sound, it is easier to isolate every instant of the experiment to differentiate it against the others. This fact tends to be more evident when increasing the playback speed, providing a fast overview of the whole experiment.

The last sonification strategy controls musical parameters, often used in electronic music, and the result itself is already musically meaningful. These parameters, such as pitch, sample triggering or effects can be controlled by a musician to compose, create a structure or to surprise. When controlled by the data it sounds rather unexpected, but the sound shows the interactions among the different selected features. Moreover, it reflects the possibilities of a musical interface controlled by the brain.

In conclusion, in order to interpret the meaning of these sonifications appropriately, the listener requires a suitable level of musical knowledge. It involves listening skills that are learned rather than innate. At a fundamental level, the **skills of decoding data from sound must be acquired**, the same as one acquires graphical interpretation skills.

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Chapter 5

Brain activity prediction

Figure 5.1: Brain activity prediction - Steps followed on the brain activity prediction approach. Sound features are firstly extracted from the original audio. Afterwards, they are used in conjunction with the corresponding fMRI images to train a brain activity model. The model is finally able to predict the resulting fMRI images of other audio stimuli.

In this chapter, we will present a computational model to predict neural activation in humans produced by auditory stimuli. The model is trained with acoustic features extracted from rhythm/no-rhythm auditory stimuli and the associated observed fMRI images. Thus, the model establishes a predictive relationship between the acoustic features extracted from the auditory stimuli and its associated neural activation. fMRI activation is predicted in two-steps: (1) encoding of stimulus signals as a set of acoustic features, and (2) prediction of the activation of each voxel in the fMRI image as a function of the acoustic features (Figure 5.1). Nevertheless, it will be only briefly explained due to a proximate article submission.

All the data used in this chapter was obtained as described in Section 4.1 . Likewise, the preprocessing applied to the data is the same as explained in Section 4.2. The next three following sections describe the acoustic feature extraction (Section 5.1), the model

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learning (Section 5.2) and the model evaluation (Section 5.3). Finally, the results will be shown in Section 5.4 and discussed in Section 5.5.

5.1 Acoustic feature extraction

Given an auditory stimulus, we initially **encode the stimulus as a vector of acoustic features** computed from the periodicity patterns of the stimulus. Clearly, the acoustic features play a central role in the approach. In order to be effective, the intermediate acoustic features must both characterize the different input stimulus signals, and factor the observed fMRI activation into more primitive components. In addition, we have chosen a set of intermediate features to be general. This is, we have selected them without assuming any of the stimuli characteristics described above. To be general and effective, the intermediate features must encode the wide variety of possible input content so that they can be linearly recombined to successfully predict the fMRI activation for arbitrary new stimuli. Motivated by previous work on rhythm characterization in arbitrary audio signals (Gou08) by Gouyon, F., we have extracted a set of acoustic features.

Briefly, the feature extraction is as follows. First, the signal is divided into small overlapping frames and computed **three low-level features** from the **spectrum** of each individual frame. In parallel, **beat times** are extracted automatically from the audio signal. The reader is referred to (GKD⁺06) for a review of algorithms that can be used for inferring tempo and beat times from audio analysis. In our work, we have used the *beatroot* algorithm (Dix07). Then, from some defined regions and the low-level features previously extracted, **four higher-level descriptors** are computed. Finally, a **periodicity descriptor** over detected beats is computed from these four higher-level descriptor sequences.

5.2 Model Learning

We have applied both **multiple regression and support vector regression** for training computational models predicting the neural fMRI activation at each voxel in the brain. The predictive models are trained by applying such methods to the features

f_i extracted from the acoustic signals and the observed fMRI images, as described in the previous section.

In the case of multiple regression, we predict the neural fMRI activation for each voxel location in the brain as a weighted sum of neural activations contributed by each feature. This is, we predict activation a at voxel v for stimulus s as in equation 5.1

$$a = \sum_{t=1}^N W_{vt} f_t \quad (5.1)$$

where $f_i(s)$ is the value of the i th acoustic feature for stimulus s , N is the number of features in the model, and W_{vi} is a learned weight that specifies the degree to which the i th feature activates voxel v . Thus, we are predicting the full fMRI image across all voxels in the brain for stimulus s as a weighted sum of images, one per acoustic feature f_i . Similarly, we train a model using support vector regression to predict the neural activation for each voxel in the brain. In this case, the input is first mapped onto a m -dimensional feature space using some fixed mapping, and then a linear model is constructed in this feature space. We have applied support vector regression with both linear kernel and 2nd degree polynomial kernel.

The obtained computational model can be evaluated by testing them with acoustic signals outside the training set and comparing its predicted fMRI images for these signals with the corresponding observed fMRI data.

5.3 Model Evaluation

Once a computational model is trained, we evaluate its accuracy by considering two new stimuli s_1 and s_2 and their corresponding images i_1 and i_2 . Based on the features extracted from stimulus s_1 and s_2 , the model is used to predict images p_1 and p_2 , respectively. We then proceed to compare the predicted and actual images as follows: Given that not every voxel in the brain is likely to be involved in representing the stimulus, we use only a subset of voxels for assessing the similarity between images. Thus, we apply ANOVA to the fMRI data during training (excluding the data from the two held-out images) and we select the subset of voxels containing the n ($n = 500$) voxels with higher f -value. For this subset of voxels we compute:

$$score(p_1 = i_1, p_2 = i_2) = cosineSimilarity(p_1, i_1) + cosineSimilarity(p_2, i_2) \quad (5.2)$$

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$$\text{score}(p_1 = i_2, p_2 = i_1) = \text{cosineSimilarity}(p_1, i_2) + \text{cosineSimilarity}(p_2, i_1) \quad (5.3)$$

The similarity between a predicted image p and observed image i has been calculated as the **cosine similarity between vectors** p and i , restricted to the selected subset of voxels. Cosine similarity between two vectors is computed as the dot product of the vectors normalized to unit length. We determine the correspondence between the two predicted and the two observed fMRI images selecting the one which has a higher score, computed as described in equations 5.2 and 5.3. In addition to cosine similarity we have also considered Pearson correlation between two images and obtained similar results. All results reported in this paper are obtained using cosine similarity.

5.4 Results

We have evaluated our model using fMRI data from 24 participants from the experiment explained in 4.1.

Figure 5.2: Prediction models accuracy - Leave-two-out cross validation accuracies for the computational models obtained by multiple linear regression, support vector regression (linear kernel and second degree polynomial kernel) for each subject.

We have produced a representative fMRI image for each stimulus by computing the mean fMRI response over all images corresponding to the stimulus, and subtracting

the mean of these representative images. We have trained a separate model for each of the 9 participants, using a set of 8 acoustic features. The 8 features have been selected from the original set of 32 features by applying a wrapper feature selection algorithm. This is, we have trained a classifier for predicting the class of stimulus (*i.e.* duration beat, duration non-beat, volume beat or volume non-beat) with all possible feature subsets of the original 32- feature subset, and selected the subset with higher accuracy. We have evaluated each trained model by applying the leave-two-out cross validation method, *i.e.* each model has been initially trained with all minus two of the stimuli and associated fMRI images. Each learnt model has been tested on its predictions of the fMRI images for the two held-out signals and then comparing the predictions with the corresponding actual held-out fMRI images. This comparison has been performed by identifying which images have higher cosine similarity, evaluated over the most stable 500 voxels.

The obtained cross-validated accuracies of the trained model predicting the unseen fMRI images for the participants by applying support vector regression with linear kernel have a mean of 0.81. The accuracies obtained by linear regression and support vector regression (both with linear and polynomial kernels) are shown in Figure 5.2. Thus, the **accuracies** for the participants are significantly above chance levels. The computational models correctly distinguish pairs of previously unseen stimuli in **81%**.

5.5 Discussion

Our approach to fMRI activity prediction is based on **two key assumptions**. It assumes (1) that the acoustic features extracted from the signal capture the rhythmical content of the stimuli, and (2) that the brain activity observed when listening to any auditory signal can be modelled by the techniques considered in Section 5.2, *i.e.* linear regression and support vector regression. The first assumption is drawn from the field of music perception and cognition where energy and spectral features are often used to characterize acoustic signals. The second assumption may be seen as consistent with the widespread use of linear models in fMRI analysis (?) and with the assumption that fMRI activation often reflects a linear superposition of contributions from different sources.

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As illustrated in Figure 5.3, the learnt computational models may accurately predict fMRI images for stimuli outside the training set. In Figure 5.3 the model has been trained leaving out the images of duration beat and duration non-beat stimuli. Although the predicted images for the left-out stimuli are not identical to the actual images, they capture aspects of the actual activation.

Figure 5.3: Observed-Predicted fMRI comparison - Predicted (top row) and observed (bottom row) fMRI images for duration beat (left column) and duration non-beat (right column) for stimuli held-out during training.

The computational model predicts with different degrees of accuracy the activation of different brain locations. This may be due to the fact that not all brain locations are involved to the same extent in encoding the input stimuli. In order to visualize the model accuracy across the brain, we have plotted the brain regions where the model's predicted activations for held-out stimuli best correlate with the observed activations average from all participants (see Figure 5.4).

Figure 5.4: Regions of most accurately predicted voxels. - The rendering shows the voxels with minimum average prediction errors over all the participants. Darker blue indicates higher accuracy.

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Chapter 6

Conclusions and future work

6.1 fMRI Sonification

In Chapter 4 we have proposed a sonification tool for exploratory fMRI data analysis. The goal has been to create a tool to allow the auditory identification of cognitive states produced by different stimuli. The implemented system consists of: preprocessing, data analysis, feature selection, visualization and sonification.

The fMRI experiments produce large amount of high dimensional, sparse and noisy data. Due to its nature, the preprocessing step has been essential, previous to any other analysis. That has included motion correction, and spatial and temporal smoothing to improve the signal to noise ratio.

Feature selection is also indispensable when dealing with neuroimaging data, that usually has a lot of features and fewer examples. we have, therefore, investigated several different methods to select most informative features, suitable for our kind of data. Specifically, three techniques have been used: T-test, ANOVA and weights of SVM. The results indicate that they seem to convey enough information for cognitive state identification, and are appropriate to train a classifier or to be used as sonification parameters.

For the sonification engine we have explored different strategies of data to sound mapping. The first strategy creates complex texture sounds, using a large amount of features coming from the data. The next two strategies incorporate harmonic relationships to express the hidden structures of the data. The last strategy explores the

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potential of these tools as brain computer interfaces. Finally, we have added visualization and interactive features to incorporate the benefits of both techniques.

The results seem to indicate that the fMRI data considered contain sufficient information to identify different cognitive states by sonifying a small number of features (*i.e.* 20 voxels) extracted from the studied fMRI data, and with no prior anatomical knowledge. The problem is that to interpret the meaning of these sonifications appropriately, the researcher requires a suitable level of experience, musical knowledge and listening skills that are learned rather than innate. At a fundamental level, the skills of decoding data from sound must be acquired, the same as one acquires graphical interpretation skills.

As future work, we plan to explore additional feature extraction methods and to conduct a series of experiments to quantitatively evaluate the system. To improve the system, it would be necessary to use new data of different nature. Moreover, it is indispensable to have constant evaluation and collaboration with neuroscientists to solve all possible design issues.

6.2 Brain Activity prediction

In the approach of Chapter 5 we have presented a computational model which predicts the fMRI neural activation in humans produced by auditory stimuli. We have shown that there is a direct relationship between energy and timbre low-level features extracted from an acoustic signal and the neural activation associated with listening to such acoustic signal.

To that end, we have trained a model with acoustic features extracted from rhythm/no-rhythm auditory stimuli and the associated observed fMRI images. The algorithm works in two steps: the encoding of stimulus signal as a set of acoustic features, and the prediction of the activation of each voxel in the fMRI image as a function of the acoustic features. Once the computational model was trained, we have evaluated its accuracy by applying the leave-two-out cross validation method, *i.e.* each model initially trained with all minus two of the stimuli and associated fMRI images. The model has shown to be capable to predict fMRI neural activity associated with the stimuli considered with accuracies far above those expected by chance.

The approach to fMRI activity prediction is based on two key assumptions. It assumes that the acoustic features extracted from the signal capture the rhythmical content of the stimuli, and that the brain activity observed when listening to any auditory signal can be modelled by the techniques proposed.

An important question is whether the trained computational models are able to extrapolate, to predict accurately rhythm stimuli belonging to categories not included in the training set. In order to test this, we would have to proceed to repeatedly train the models with less than the available stimuli categories (*i.e.* 3 out of 4) and associated fMRI images.

To create more general models it will be essential to conduct new experiments with richer and different type of auditory stimuli, as well as using different kind of acoustic and musical features.

Furthermore, the computational models trained to make these predictions provide insight into how the neural activity that represents music can be decomposed into a basis set of neural activation patterns associated with different acoustical features of music. The work is related to recent research that uses machine learning algorithms to train classifiers of mental states based on fMRI. However, it differs in that our models are capable of extrapolating to predict fMRI images for mental states not present in the training set. The potential of this approach is the possibility to create new neural activity from auditory stimuli. This might bring enormous advantages on the study of how music is encoded in the brain.

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Appendix

“A data sonification approach to cognitive state identification”, published at the 17th International Conference on Auditory Display (ICAD-2011) (GR11), by Imanol Gómez and Rafael Ramírez.

A DATA SONIFICATION APPROACH TO COGNITIVE STATE IDENTIFICATION

Imanol Gomez

Univeristat Pompeu Fabra
Music Tecnology Group
Tanger 122-138
08018 Barcelona, Spain

imanol.gomez01@estudiant.upf.edu

Rafael Ramirez

Univeristat Pompeu Fabra
Music Tecnology Group
Tanger 122-138
08018 Barcelona, Spain

rafael.ramirez@upf.edu

ABSTRACT

The study of human brain functions has dramatically increased greatly due to the advent of Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging (fMRI), arguably the best technique for observing human brain activity that is currently available. However, fMRI techniques produce extremely high dimensional, sparse and noisy data which is difficult to visualize, monitor and analyze. In this paper, we propose two different sonification approaches to monitor fMRI data. The goal of the resulting fMRI data sonification system is to allow the auditory identification of cognitive states produced by different stimuli. The system consists of a feature selection component and a sonification engine. We explore different feature selection methods and sonification strategies. As a case study, we apply our system to the identification of cognitive states produced by volume accented and duration accented rhythmic stimuli.

1. INTRODUCTION

The human brain is an extremely complex information processing system and the understanding of most of its functions is still a major challenge. Many techniques have been developed to detect and measure neural activity in humans (e.g. EEG, fMRI, CAT) and various methods have been proposed for analyzing the resulting data. In particular, Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging (fMRI) has been used extensively to test hypothesis regarding the location of activation for different brain functions. However, fMRI provides extremely high dimensional, sparse and noisy data which is difficult to visualize, monitor and analyze.

The goal of exploratory data analysis is to render high dimensional data in such a way that we can use our natural pattern recognition capabilities in order to search for regularities and structures. This approach has mainly focused on human visual capabilities. Many visualization techniques have been developed such as Self-Organizing Maps [1, 2], Multidimensional Scaling [3] and Projection Pursuit [4] which creates low-dimensional imaging of the original data.

Motivated by the acknowledged human capacity to make accurate and rapid processing and discrimination of sounds, in this paper we investigate human auditory perception for exploring and analyzing fMRI data. In particular, we propose a sonification approach to monitor and exploring fMRI data. Our goal is to allow the auditory identification of cognitive states produced by different stimuli. The detection of sequences of cognitive states can help in the diagnosis of difficulties in performing a complex task. We have implemented a system consisting of two parts: a feature

selection component, and a sonification engine. For the feature selection component we investigate different feature selection methods, while for the sonification engine we explore different data to sound mapping strategies. We apply our system to fMRI data produced by auditory stimuli consisting of rhythmic and non-rhythmic audio signals.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 sets out the background for this research. In Section 3, we describe our approach to fMRI data sonification, and finally Section 4 presents some conclusions and indicates some areas of future research.

2. BACKGROUND

2.1. Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging

Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging (fMRI) is a brain imaging technique that allows the observation of brain activity in human subjects based on the increase in blood flow to the local vasculature that accompanies neural activity in the brain. More precisely, fMRI measures the ratio of oxygenated hemoglobin to deoxygenated hemoglobin in the blood with respect to a control baseline, at many individual locations within the brain. The blood oxygen level is believed to be influenced by local neural activity, and thus this blood oxygen level dependent (BOLD) response is normally taken as an indicator of neural activity. An fMRI scanner measures the value of the fMRI signal (BOLD response) at all the points in a three dimensional image.

An fMRI scanner produces time-series data that represents brain activity in a collection of 2D slices of the brain. The collection of the 2D slices form a 3D image of the brain containing in the order of 60000 voxels, i.e. cubes of tissue about 2 millimeters on each side. Images are usually taken every 1-5 seconds. Despite the limitations in temporal resolution, fMRI is arguably the best technique for observing human brain activity that is currently available. While the spatial resolution of fMRI is dramatically better than that provided by earlier brain imaging methods, each voxel nevertheless contains on the order of hundreds of thousands of neurons. Figure 1 shows fMRI data collected while a person listened to auditory stimuli.

fMRI has been widely applied to the task of identifying the regions in the brain which are activated when a human performs a particular cognitive function. Most of the reported research summarizes average fMRI responses when a human is presented with a particular stimulus repeatedly. Regions in the brain activated by a particular task are identified by comparing fMRI activity during the period where the stimulus is presented with the activity de-

Figure 1: fMRI data collected while a person listened to auditory stimuli. The figure represents nine 2D slices from a 3D image of the brain. Every slice is 64x64 voxels and their intensities are represented with a "jet" colormap. This colormap begins with blue (lowest intensity), and passes through cyan, yellow, orange, and red (highest intensity).

tected under a control condition. In this paper, the aim is to identify different cognitive states from fMRI data using sonification.

2.2. Sonification

Sonification refers to the use of (non-speech) audio in order to convey information about data. Due to the characteristics of auditory perception, such as excellent temporal and pressure resolution, sonification provides an interesting alternative or complement to visualization techniques. Sonification has been a well established technique in applications that require a constant awareness of some information (e.g. vital body functions during an operation). Success stories of sonification include the Geiger counter, sonar, the auditory thermometer, and numerous medical auditory displays. Recently, several tools have been developed to explore data streams through sonification. This is the case of Sonifyer, a Mac users interface for listening to data, mainly based on audification and FM synthesis [5]. Two other sonification tools are AeSon Toolkit which is motivated by user-centred customisation of the aesthetic representation and scope of the data [6], and SUMO [7] for the sonification of chemical data.

Nowadays, with abundance of high-dimensional data, auditory data exploration has become an important tool to comprehend high-dimensional data and to uncover important structures and patterns [8, 9] in complex data. It is particularly appropriate to improve insight into biomedical data, which are naturally multidimensional. Sonification based on Electroencephalography (EEG) has been widely used for the study of the brain [10, 11, 12, 13].

One of the first attempts to auditory EEG exploration was reported in 1934 by E. Adrian and B. Matthews [10]. They measured the brain activity from a human subject by electrodes applied to the head, and the channels were viewed optically on bromide paper using the Matthews oscillograph, while being directly transduced into sound. They could demonstrate the synchronization between brain activity and external stimuli.

More recently, T. Hermann et al. in 2002 [11] presented dif-

ferent strategies of sonification for human EEG: *spectral mapping*, by analysing the spectral properties of the signals; *Distance Matrix Sonification*, using the Euclidean distance among all signals; and *Differential Sonification*, where they compare the data from different conditions and different channels.

In [14] T. Hermann and G. Baier analysed the rhythmical structure of EEG using auditory exploration. They used a set of differential equations to process the data and extract the parameters to feed the Model-Based Sonification [15]. In 2006 T. Hermann and G. Baier [16] used an articulatory speech model driven by variable features. Both personalized and generic features were used, such as transient activity, spatial distribution or correlation matrix features. T. Hermann and G. Baier also explored multi-channel sonification [13]. The system was intended to allow the listener to perceive spatial characteristics of the data in a multi-speaker environment. They explored the idea of *Event-Based Sonification* (EBS), where features are defined as events that trigger sound synthesis. In this case, local maxima was thought to be suitable both for real-time sonifications and meaningful to the clinician.

There has also been attempts to translate human EEG into music. D. Wu et al. worked to represent mental states by using music [17]. The EEG features were extracted by wavelet analysis and they would control musical parameters such as pitch, tempo, rhythm, and tonality. To give more musically meaning, some rules were taken into account like harmony or structure. One of the main challenges of this work was to find the precise trade-off between directly sonification of the features and music composition.

However, to the best of our knowledge, no similar research projects based on fMRI data have been reported in the scientific literature.

3. THE FMRI SONIFICATION SYSTEM

3.1. Feature Selection

Given the high dimensionality of the data considered, before any attempt to sonification it is necessary to apply feature selection methods. In this paper, we explore the following feature selection strategies:

- **Voxel discriminability.** For each voxel and considered cognitive state, a t-test is performed comparing the fMRI activity of the voxel in examples belonging to the two stimuli of interest. In the case of more than two cognitive states, instead of the t-test, an f-test is performed comparing the fMRI of the voxel in examples belonging to the different stimuli of interest. n voxels are then selected by choosing the ones with larger t-values.
- **Voxel activity.** For each voxel and considered cognitive state, a t-test is performed comparing the fMRI activity of the voxel in examples belonging to a particular stimulus to its activity in examples belonging to fixation periods. For each cognitive state, n voxels are then selected by choosing the ones with larger t-values. Note that these voxels may discriminate only one target class from fixation.

The feature selection strategies are motivated by the fact that fMRI binary cognitive state identification problems naturally give rise to three types of data (similarly for non-binary identification problems): data corresponding to the two target classes, C1 and C2, and data corresponding to the fixation condition. Data corresponding to C1 and C2 is composed of signal plus noise, while

data corresponding to the fixation condition contains only noise, i.e. it contains no relevant signal. Thus, two natural feature selection methods are voxel discriminability, i.e. how well the feature discriminates C1 and C2, and voxel activity, i.e. how well the feature distinguishes C1 or C2 from the fixation class. While the former selection method is a straightforward method for selecting voxels which discriminate the two classes, the later focuses on choosing voxels with large signal-to-noise ratios, although it ignores whether the feature actually discriminates the two classes. Within the fMRI community it is common to use voxel activity to select a subset of relevant voxels.

In conjunction with the voxel discriminability and voxel activity strategies, we have explored *Spherical Multivariate Searchlight*. Spherical Multivariate Searchlight is used to obtain a continuous map in which informative regions are marked, by moving a spherical multivariate searchlight through the measured volume of brain activity. The searchlight is centered on each voxel in turn. To combine the signals from all voxels falling into the searchlight, we compute the average of their t-values.

3.2. Voxel sonification

The core of sonification is the processes and algorithms that define the mapping of data to sound for any particular application. The term mapping refers, to mathematical transformations applied to real-time data received from controllers or sensors so that they may be used as effective control for sound synthesis parameters.

For our purpose we have used Parameter-Mapping Sonification, in which data values are mapped to the various parameters of a sound. This approach is particularly suited for multivariate representation, as many data dimensions can be listened to at the same time. Nevertheless, connecting the parameters to components of a real-time sound synthesis system is not trivial.

To effectively perform a musically satisfying mapping, we must understand well the nature of the data sources and the nature of the sounds and music we want to produce. This poses significant problems in the case of biologically controlled sonification in that the goal is to have an unambiguous interpretation of the meaning of biological signals whether direct or derived. Moreover, we should ask ourselves, how should human brain activity sound? how consistent would a sonar interpretation be for various listeners?

The artificial sound synthesis has been implemented by additive synthesis controlled by the features extracted from the data as explained in section 3.1. According to this technique, we have implemented and compared two different sonifications strategies.

In the first approach, every selected feature controls the level of a single note, creating minor blues chords, within several octaves. In order to do that every feature is normalized by its energy activation range to avoid preferences on higher energetic features. However, for each time instant, only the five features with highest activation value will be synthesized. Hence, a singular sound will be created at every instant by means of timbre, pitch and loudness, that represents the activation patterns of the selected features. The intension of this approach is to create harmonic and pleasant sounds. However, the number of extracted features must remain low, limited by the number of octaves that the human auditory system is able to perceive. A sonification sample using this approach can be found at www.upf.dtic.edu/~rramirez/blues.mp3.

The second sonification strategy uses a larger number of features, approximately 200. The idea is to create a sound tex-

ture, that would represent the data by summing partials with additive synthesis. In this case, the normalized energy from every feature is mapped to the frequency of a sine tone within the human hearing range. The resulting sound has a noisy nature due to the fact that there are no harmonic restrictions. Nonetheless, it is the representation of the evolution of the selected features across time. A fragment of the sound spectrogram can be seen in Figure 2 and a sonification sample can be found at www.upf.dtic.edu/~rramirez/additive.mp3.

The chosen software environment for sonification has been Pure Data [18], since it makes available rapid prototyping of real-time sound generators. It also supports the Open Sound Control protocol for communication between the core and the sound generator. A piece of the sound engine for the first approach can be seen at Figure 3.

Finally, the combination of both visualization and sonification of the data may lead to a better understanding of it. For that purpose, we have implemented an interface, Figure 4, that allows the user to visually explore the data, while hearing the sonification of the selected features, as explained in section 3.1.

Figure 2: Sound spectrogram fragment from the second sonification approach. The x and y axes represent time and frequency respectively, and the color represents the intensity of the frequency components. The horizontal lines show the partials mapped from the selected features and the vertical lines is the consequence of the abrupt transitions between time slots.

3.3. Experiments and data

The fMRI data used in this study was produced by volume accented and duration accented rhythmic stimuli were used. The stimuli were between 14 and 18 s long. There were four rhythm types: volume beat, volume non-beat, duration beat and duration non-beat. Thus, the first rhythm type (Volume accented with Beat) consisted of 81 tones, in which every 4th tone was louder by 6.6 dB, in order to give rise to the perception of a regular beat (occurring 21 times per trial). For each trial, the tone length was chosen from a range of 180 to 228 ms (in 8 ms steps) so that a new beat would be induced in each trial, not simply carried over from a previous trial. Accordingly, the beat occurred at a rate of 720 to 912 ms. The second rhythm type (Volume accented with no beat) also had 81 tones. However, the tone volumes were not isochronous, so no regular beat could be fit to the rhythm.

Figure 4: fMRI Data Interface. The plots at the top and at the bottom left represent three different slices of a 3D image of the brain, according to the X,Y, Z axes. The fourth plot represents the energy of the voxel selected by the user, across time. The bottom panel is used a video player and the left panel shows different information about the system and the selected voxel.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

We have proposed two different fMRI data sonification approaches to cognitive state identification. The first approach brings a harmonic sonification to explore the data by using blues chords as reference. The second approach creates a complex texture sound by using a large amount of features coming from the data.

The system's objective is the auditory detection of cognitive states produced by different auditory stimuli, and combines sonification and visualization in order to incorporate the benefits of both techniques. We have explored different feature selection techniques in order to reduce the dimensionality of the data before sonification. In particular we have explored voxel discriminability and voxel activity feature selection. The work reported is still in progress but the results we have so far obtained are encouraging. This preliminary results seem to indicate that the fMRI data considered contain sufficient information to identify different cognitive states by sonifying a small number of features (i.e. 20 voxels) extracted from the studied fMRI data, and with no prior anatomical knowledge. The problem provides a very interesting instance of sonification with extremely high dimensional, sparse and noisy data. As future work, we plan to explore additional feature extraction methods and to conduct a series of experiments for quantitatively evaluating the system.

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